

Natural enemy density (total / 5 hills)

2. Relationship between pest and natural enemy density in Arisol (A) and Sindri (S), in 3 successive samples (1, 2, and 3).

Species composition and seasonal occurrence of rice green leafhoppers (GLH) in Nepal

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Rice GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus* were collected from ricefields and nurseries at six sites in Chitwan and one site each in Bara (Parwanipur) and Janakpur (Hardinath) Districts of Nepal. In Saradanagar and Mangalpur, Chitwan, samples were collected at 2- to 3-wk intervals Apr-Oct 1989; in the remaining four sites, samples were collected once, during the fourth week of Aug 1989.

Each sample consisted of insects captured by an insect net in 30-40 horizontal sweeps in an arc approximately 1 m wide. At IAAS, a general-purpose black-light insect survey trap with a fluorescent 15-W bulb was set up very close to a ricefield and operated down to dusk. Leafhoppers were trapped and counted at about 1-mo intervals Jun-Dec 1989.

Composition of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* collected at most sites varied considerably: numbers of *N. virescens* were much higher. The ratio of *N. virescens* to *N. nigropictus* varied from 13.8 to 41.0; the highest ratios were in Parwanipur (Bara) and Sripur (Chitwan) and the lowest in Hardinath (Dhanusha)

Table 1. Species composition, and population density of *Nephotettix* spp. collected by net sweeps in ricefields in Chitwan, Bara, and Janakpur Districts of Nepal, Aug 1989.

Locality	District	Leafhoppers ^a (no.)				Ratio ^b
		<i>N. virescens</i>		<i>N. nigropictus</i>		
		Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD	
Sripur	Chitwan	4-16	8.2±4	0-2	0.2	41.0
Gopalganj	Chitwan	3-6	4.6±1	0	0	
Shivnagar	Chitwan	5-15	8.3±3	0	0	
Jaynagar	Chitwan	7-50	18.0±16	0	0	
Saradanagar	Chitwan	7-28	11.9±5	1-3	0.5±1	23.8
Mangalpur	Chitwan	7-25	12.8±5	0-4	0.4±1	32.0
Parwanipur	Bara	7-132	89.4±22	1-5	2.2±.9	40.6
Hardinath	Dhanusha	3-6	8.3±1	2-3	0.6±1	13.8

^a Seven to ten net-sweeping surveys of 30-40 strokes was standard at each collection site. ^b *N. virescens*:*N. nigropictus*.

Table 2. Population of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* captured by net-sweeping in ricefields at Saradanagar and Mangalpur, Chitwan, Nepal, Apr-Oct 1989.

Collection date	Leafhoppers collected/30-40 sweeps (no.)							
	Mangalpur				Saradanagar			
	<i>N. virescens</i>		<i>N. nigropictus</i>		<i>N. virescens</i>		<i>N. nigropictus</i>	
	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD	Range	Mean ± SD
22 Apr	0-1	0.14±3	0-1	0.43±.5	0-1	0.2 ± .4	1-3	1.7±1
9 May	1-2	2.00±1	0	0.00	0-3	1.1 ± .7	0	0
24 May	0-1	0.10	0	0.00	-	-	-	-
8 Jun	-	-	-	-	0	0.00	0	0
15 Jun	-	-	-	-	1-4	2.3 ± 1	0	0
22 Jun	-	-	-	-	0-1	0.75±.4	0	0
29 Jun	-	-	-	-	2-8	5.30±2	0	0
6 Aug	1-16	5.00±4	0	0.00	1-3	2.50±2	0	0
21 Aug	7-28	1.90±5	0-1	0.46±.9	7-25	12.80±5	1-4	0.40±.2
9 Sep	10-95	47.80±6	0-5	1.60±5	12-52	36.5 ± 6	2-5	3.10±1
9 Oct	61-139	99.90±5	2-8	3.80±4	198-355	274.4 ± 4	1-8	5.90±.5

(Table 1). Irrespective of site, the overall ratio of *N. virescens* to *N. nigropictus* was 41.0.

Populations of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* varied, depending on site and time of collection. At all sites, *N. virescens* was much more numerous than *N. nigropictus* (Table 2). The population of *N. virescens* was larger in Parwanipur than in Hardinath and Chitwan.

In monthly sweep-net catches at Saradanagar and Mangalpur, Chitwan, GLH numbers ranged from 0 to 355. The population increased sharply in Aug-Sep, peaked during Oct-Nov, and sharply declined in Dec.

N. nigropictus populations fluctuated at low levels at all sites, but was highest in Parwanipur. At Saradanagar and Mangalpur sites, the population had two

peaks: the first in May, with a population decline Jun to mid-Aug, then another increase from Aug to peak again Sep-Oct, then a sharp decline. ■

Brown mirid bug, a new predator of brown planthopper (BPH) in the Philippines

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Three species of mirids have been reported as important predators of rice planthoppers. In the Philippines, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* has been well discussed. Recently, a species belonging to the genus *Tytthus* was found surviving on BPH colonies in the greenhouse. It is